

Spectral and Magnetic Studies of Some Mixed Ligand Complexes of High-Spin Cobalt(II)

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DIVALENT cobalt complexes have tendency towards oxidation in presence of a variety of complexing agents¹. The complexes synthesized in the present study have been found to be sufficiently stable and resistant to oxidation. In these ligand exchange reactions the comparatively weak bonded coordinated water molecules of the parent β -ketoester complexes of Co(II) are quantitatively replaced by thiourea. Since the solubility of these complexes in common organic solvents has been found to be very low, the diffuse reflectance has been carried out using lithium fluoride as diluent as well as reference.

Experimental

Diaquo *bis*-(methylacetoacetato) and diaquo *bis*-(ethylacetoacetato) of Co(II) were prepared by known method². The mixed ligand complexes were synthesized by adding an ethanolic solution of the second ligand viz. thiourea or phenylthiourea (0.02 mole) to an ethanolic solution of diaquo *bis*-(MeAA) Co(II) or diaquo *bis*-(EtAA) Co(II) (0.01 mole). The resulting reaction mixture was refluxed for one and half hour. The complex separated out on cooling, was filtered, washed with ethanol and ether and dried *in vacuo* over anhydrous calcium chloride.

Magnetic measurements were made on a Gouy magnetic balance at $300 \pm 1^\circ\text{K}$. The ir spectra of the complexes were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer in KBr phase while diffuse reflectance spectra were recorded on a VEB Carl Zeiss Jena VSU 2P spectrophotometer using the reflectance attachment o/r.

Results and Discussion

The magnetic moment (μ_{eff}) for all the complexes ranges between 4.95-5.28 B.M. (Table 1)

indicating the complexes to be high-spin complexes with three unpaired electrons and having almost octahedral stereochemistry^{3,4}. Absence of absorption band around 3450 cm^{-1} in the mixed ligand complexes, discernible in parent complexes, show the replacement of two coordinated water molecules of parent complexes by two thiourea ligands. A considerable overlapping of bands due to coordinated β -ketoesters and the second ligand was observed. Definite shifts were observed in C-O, C-C and M-O stretching frequencies (Table 1) on coordination of thiourea ligands, because all the three bands are involved in the resonance system. The direction of these shifts cannot be correctly predicted since there will be a metal-ligand π bonding superimposed on a ligand-metal bond⁵. The shift of -NH absorption vibration of thiourea ligands towards higher and that of C=S band (around 740 cm^{-1}) towards lower frequency regions suggest the coordination of thiourea or substituted thiourea ligand to the metal through S-atom^{6,7}.

In high-spin cobalt(II) complexes, the experimentally observed spin-allowed transitions in increasing order of energy are ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$, and are denoted as ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 , respectively⁸. By using transitions ν_1 and ν_3 , and following weak field coupling scheme, the values for Racah interelectronic repulsion parameter, B, and crystal field splitting energy parameter, $10Dq$, have been calculated⁹ and are summarized in Table 1 along with experimentally observed transition energies. In the calculation of the different parameters the transition band ν_2 has not been used since it is a weak band due to two electron jump and hence its accurate location is difficult. The Jahn-Teller effect in the ground state ${}^4T_{1g}(F)$ of octahedral d^7 ion is expected to be weak and has not been considered here. The value of the free gaseous ion, 972 cm^{-1} , is used to calculate the value for nephelauxetic ratio, β . The lower values for β in these mixed ligand complexes as compared to their respective parent complexes indicate the increase in covalency on further complexation. By using the modified Tanabe-Sugano diagram given by Lever¹⁰, the graphical values for parameters B and $10Dq$ have been deduced using transition energy ratio ν_3/ν_1 (Table 1).

TABLE 1—EXPERIMENTALLY OBSERVED TRANSITION ENERGIES, VALUES OF VARIOUS PARAMETERS AND IR SPECTRAL DATA (IN CM^{-1})

Complex	${}^4T_{1g}(F)$ ↓ ${}^4T_{2g}$	${}^4T_{1g}(F)$ ↓ ${}^4A_{2g}$	${}^4T_{1g}(F)$ ↓ ${}^4T_{1g}(P)$	B	10 Dq	B (Graph)	10 Dq (Graph)	ν_3/ν_1	β	$\nu(\text{C-O})$	$\nu(\text{C-C})$	$\nu(\text{M-O})$
Co(MeAA) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	8547	19801	21505	944.7	9759	954.5	9831	2.51	0.97	1620 s	1505 s	450 m
Co(MeAA) ₂ (TU) ₂	8333	17842	20619	890.1	9397	902.7	9388	2.47	0.91	1630 s	1490 m	465 m
Co(MeAA) ₂ (PTU) ₂	8474	18975	21276	933.8	9676	936.0	9640	2.51	0.96	1580 s	1485 s	468 w
Co(EtAA) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂	8620	19607	21739	956.8	9853	928.6	9471	2.52	0.98	1626 s	1525 s	480 m
Co(EtAA) ₂ (TU) ₂	8488	19157	20408	872.8	9660	871.7	9588	2.40	0.89	1630 s	1530 m	462 m
Co(EtAA) ₂ (PTU) ₂	8605	18867	21276	924.5	9831	926.6	9636	2.47	0.95	1547 s	1532 m	468 m

MeAA = methylacetoacetate, EtAA = ethylacetoacetate; TU = thiourea; PTU = phenylthiourea.

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Hay and Caughley⁵ have proposed the *trans* arrangement of the ligand for the β -ketoester derivatives of cobalt(II). Ballhausen *et al.*¹¹ have correlated this *trans* behaviour in cobalt(II) complexes with the width of the electronic absorption bands. The presence of narrow electronic bands was correlated to the *trans* configuration of the complexes. The electronic bands in these mixed ligand complexes also retain the same absorption pattern when the $\text{Co}(\text{MeAA})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ and $\text{Co}(\text{EtAA})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ react with thiourea and the observed bands are not broad. Thus, we can assume that the mixed ligand complexes derived from β -ketoesters of cobalt(II) have also the *trans* configuration with almost octahedral stereochemistry. Slight distortion may be due to the non-identical nature of the coordinating atoms.

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Determination of Stability Constants of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-4'-Chloro-2'-Methoxyaniline Complexes with La^{3+} , Y^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Dy^{3+} and Gd^{3+}

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It has been generally concluded from previous work¹⁻⁴ on the correlation between chelate stability and ionic radii that the stabilities of the tripositive lanthanide complexes should increase with decreasing cation radius or increasing atomic number. An examination of the stability constant data generally bears out this expectation but reveals

an anomalous behaviour in some instances. A large amount of work done relates to $\bar{O}$, $\bar{O}$ donors. However, complexes containing $\bar{O}$ and N functional groups (azomethines) have not been dealt with very extensively. This communication is a continuation of our work⁵ on Schiff bases. The new Schiff base, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-chloro-2'-methoxyaniline has been selected to study a correlation, if any, between the stability constants and the ionic potentials of the trivalent lanthanides.

Experimental

The ligand 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-chloro-2'-methoxyaniline was synthesised and repeatedly crystallised from alcohol to get an analytically pure sample with m.p. 271° (observed). All reagents were of A. R. grade and their solutions were made in purified dioxan⁶ and double distilled CO_2 free water. pH metric titrations of the following solutions, (i-iii) were carried out at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ under nitrogen atmosphere. These solutions, with an initial volume of 40 ml, were titrated with a carbonate free standard sodium hydroxide solution (1.07 M) using a Corning Model 12 precision research pH meter having an accuracy of 0.005 pH unit with combined glass electrode and calomel reference electrode. The medium of titration was 75 : 25 (v/v) dioxan-water mixture. A constant ionic strength (0.1 M) was maintained by adding requisite amount of NaClO_4 .

- (i) 5 ml (0.16 M) HClO_4 + 5 ml (0.64 M) NaClO_4 + 30 ml dioxan.
- (ii) 5 ml (0.16 M) HClO_4 + 5 ml (0.64 M) NaClO_4 + 49.84 mg reagent, accurately weighed to give 0.004 M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml dioxan.
- (iii) 5 ml (0.64 M) NaClO_4 + 5 ml metal salt (0.008 M) solution in (0.16 M) HClO_4 + 49.84 mg reagent accurately weighed to give 0.004 M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml of dioxan.

The experimental method of Irving and Rossotti⁷ was applied to find out the values of $\bar{n}$ and pL . The titrations were performed in duplicate to test for reproducibility.

Results and Discussion

It may be pointed out here that the ligand used in this study did not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions. This was indicated by rapid attainment of equilibrium during the titrations and by the absence of any significant change in pH even after 1 hr. The phenolic OH group of the ligand is deprotonated during complex formation.

From the titration curves of solutions (i) and (ii), $\bar{n}_A$ values at various 'B' values (pH meter readings), were calculated and a curve between 'B' and the corresponding $\bar{n}_A$ values was plotted. The value of pK_1^H was evaluated by half integral method as well as from the plot of $\log(\bar{n}_A/1-\bar{n}_A)$ vs B. Both these values agree well.